

Maternal Healthcare Financing and Utilization in Kashmir : An Empirical Evidence

NUSRATH JAN AND MOHIUD DIN SANGMI

Abstract : *This study attempts to evaluate the working of Maternal Healthcare Financing Schemes which have been designed for women of reproductive age in India. However, the study has been restricted to Jammu and Kashmir UT only. A Multistage Stratified Sampling technique has been used for the survey, following a well-structured and pretested Interview Schedule. The study has employed Quasi-Experimental Design which requires comparing a Treatment Group of beneficiaries who have availed benefits of the schemes to the Comparison Group of non-beneficiaries. The impact assessment on each indicator of Maternal Healthcare Utilization has been made by comparing two independent groups of respondents using Independent Samples Test. The results indicate significant and positive differences between the two groups under each indicator of Maternal Healthcare Utilization – Antenatal Care (ANC), Delivery Care (DC) and Postnatal Care (PNC). Moreover, the degree and intensity of impact has been computed with the help of Effect Size (r). The prime impact has been shown on delivery care mainly attributed to cash assistance provided under Janani Suraksha Yojana. Yet, the findings reveal that there are still gaps among respondents regarding awareness of the availability of cashless services in government institutions. The loopholes are especially noticeable when it comes to free and cashless benefits provided under Janani Shishu Suraksha Karyakram.*

Keywords : Maternal Healthcare Financing, Antenatal Care, Delivery Care, Postnatal Care, Quasi-Experimental Research Design.

Nusrath Jan, Research Scholar, Department of Commerce, University of Kashmir. E-mail : mirnusrath77@gmail.com. Mob : 9149629920.

Prof (Dr) Mohiud Din Sangmi, Senior Professor and Former Dean, College Development Council, Department of Commerce, University of Kashmir. Mob : 9419095039.

1. Introduction

Motherhood is one of the most cherished and critical stages in a woman's life. It is a period when she demands more attention, support and nutrition. However, the path to a safe motherhood is not easy for every woman around the world. It is estimated that nearly 536,000 women (or one woman in every minute) die annually due to maternity complications and approximately all these deaths (99 percent) occur in developing countries (United Nations, 2009; Pandey et al., 2011). South Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa together account for almost 85 percent of all maternal deaths in the world (United Nations, 2009). Due to the fact that lives of millions of mothers in the reproductive age group can be saved via the use of maternal healthcare, maternal health has become a worldwide public health concern (Gyimah et al., 2006). Maternal health refers to the health of women during pregnancy, childbirth and the postpartum period (WHO, 2022). Maternal Healthcare Utilization refers to the use of Antenatal Care (ANC), Institutionalized Delivery Care (DC) and Postnatal Care (PNC) so as to provide the continuum of care for maternal, new-born and child health. In the spectrum of maternal health, prenatal care, institutional delivery (including skilled birth attendance) and postnatal care are important milestones required to achieve optimum maternal and child health. Antenatal Care also called as pre-natal care, is the 'care before birth' to promote the well-being of mother along with her child and is essential to reduce maternal morbidity and mortality, low births, and pre-natal mortality (WHO, 2005). Delivery Care refers to care provided to women during delivery. It ensures that the woman is assisted by a skilled birth attendant i.e., someone with midwifery skills such as a doctor, a nurse or a professional midwife during delivery (Lim et al., 2010). Postnatal care often known as postpartum care outlines the care given to a woman after delivery. Utilization of institution based Antenatal Care, Delivery Care, and Postnatal Care continues to be low, especially in remote and scattered habitations (Peters et al. 2002; International Institute for Population Sciences 2007). In most economically developing nations, low utilisation of maternal healthcare is a major concern, and India is no exception. Despite improvements in boosting maternal healthcare availability, the majority of women in India still lack complete access to healthcare. Low ANC utilisation, combined with severely low-skilled delivery and PNC use, is well recognised as one of the key predictors of a high maternal mortality ratio in India. Therefore, utilization of maternal healthcare has now become global and national priority and a prerequisite for attaining Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), since one of the SDGs is to reduce global maternal

mortality to less than 70 per 100,000 live births by 2030, to achieve universal health coverage for sexual and reproductive health (SDGs- Maternity Worldwide). Realising the significance of Maternal Healthcare in the modern times, India has recently dabbled in this field aggressively and undertook massive investments in maternal and child health through various public health interventions. Several projects have been implemented by Government of India at the national level and by the respective State Governments at the sub-national levels in the last two decades (Singh and Vellakkal, 2021). The various interventions/schemes in Public Health are described as :-

- (i) Janani Suraksha Yojana (JSY)
- (ii) Janani Shishu Suraksha Karyakram (JSSK)

JSY is a Conditional Cash Transfer Scheme which aims to provide financial assistance to expectant mothers to encourage use of maternal healthcare during pre-natal, delivery and post-partum period. The scheme has been implemented with the objective of reducing maternal and neo-natal mortality by promoting institutional delivery among poor expectant women. ASHA, an accredited social health activist, has been identified as a plausible interface between the government and disadvantaged expectant women by the Yojana (National Health Portal, 2015). In 2011, Government of India launched Janani Shishu Suraksha Karyakram (JSSK) to provide free and cashless services to expectant women for both Caesarean Section and normal delivery and new borns up-to thirty days in government health institutions. Besides, the scheme provides various free entitlements including free diagnostics, medicines, provision of blood and transport facility without any user fees (MoH&FW, 2011). These initiatives are part of a broader policy aimed at achieving Universal Health Care (UHC) in India. Various policy documents outlining India's health vision have emphasised that achieving UHC is a priority (HLEG, 2011).

Previous studies have assessed women's utilization of a single maternal health service, particularly skilled birth delivery (Prinja et al., 2015; Randive et al., 2013; 2014) but none considered the complete utilization of all three services and its impact on overall maternal health outcomes. Moreover, none of the studies addressing this issue have been conducted in the Union Territory of Jammu and Kashmir so far. Therefore, the present study is aimed to fill this gap in the existing literature and make a modest contribution in the field.

2. Review of Literature:

One of the elements contributing to increased maternal and newborn mortality and morbidity is low usage of maternal healthcare services. Poor people, according to available literature, rarely use free public health care (UNDP, 2004). In Bangladesh, the low utilisation of maternal health services is attributed to supply-side issues and demand-side constraints. Non-availability of maternity and newborn health services, pharmaceuticals, and consumables, discrimination against impoverished women, and the imposition of unofficial user fees are all supply-side challenges. Demand-side hurdles include cultural and social belief systems, social taboo associated with pregnancy and child birth, distance from home to nearest health centre, lack of information on sources of care, lack of awareness of the benefit of maternal health services, and high access costs (direct and indirect) (Ensor, 2004; Ahmad and Khan, 2011).

Numerous research studies have sought to evaluate the impact of Maternal Healthcare Financing Schemes in various contexts. Some of them have discovered that the programs have a positive impact on maternal healthcare utilisation, as well as the other way around. Lagarde and colleagues conducted a systematic review to evaluate the impact of conditional cash transfer schemes (targeting poor and disadvantaged sections, primarily pregnant and lactating mothers, infants, and children) in low- and middle-income countries in terms of improving health outcomes and access to healthcare services. The study concludes that conditional cash transfers can help people use health services and improve their health outcomes, while the size and importance of the effect varies. CCTs' impact and success, however, can be influenced by a range of factors on both the demand and supply sides (Lagarde et al., 2009). Another study from Argentina indicated that the Plan Nacer Program had a favourable impact on low-income mothers by improving access to comprehensive maternity and child health services (Cortez and Romero, 2013). According to Ahmed and Khan (2011), the introduction of a maternal health voucher scheme in Bangladesh increased demand for prenatal, delivery, and postnatal care services, particularly among poor women in the community, and hence the intervention had a beneficial influence on health-care utilisation. A demand-side financing program, however, may not be effective in the absence of local health service capacity, according to the study, unless significant development of the health facility's service delivery capacity occurs. As per Nguyen et al. (2012), a study conducted in Bangladesh on 2208 women of which comprising 1104 as Treatment Group and 1104 as Control Group, the voucher plan had a beneficial influence on maternal service utilisation. As a result, the recipients were more likely to use skilled practitioners'

support for prenatal, delivery, and postnatal care. In their study, Axelson et al. (2009) discovered that the program has a considerable impact on the use of health services among the impoverished Vietnamese people. Several studies conducted in Indian context have also demonstrated that demand side financing programs such as JSY and JSSK have a favourable impact on access to and utilisation of maternal health care services (Gopalan and Durairaj, 2012; Randive et al., 2013; Randive et al., 2014; Prinja et al., 2015; Mohanty and Kastor, 2017; Sen et al., 2020). Various research studies, however, have found a negative or no effect on utilization (Mondal et al. 2015; Powell Jackson et al., 2015). The present unexplored study, henceforth, is a humble attempt to validate these findings and get insights on unclear impact of Maternal Healthcare Financing Schemes in raising maternal utilisation among marginalised women. Moreover, numerous studies suggest that demand side financing schemes have dramatically increased institutional births (Lim et al., 2010; Rahman and Pallikadavath, 2018; Ali et al., 2019). The studies, however, have been unable to determine whether Maternal Healthcare Financing Schemes help to improve prenatal and postnatal care (Powell-Jackson et al., 2015; Brauw and Peterman, 2020). Therefore, the current study may attempt to fill this vacuum in the literature by taking all the three maternal healthcare services into consideration.

3. Objectives and Hypotheses

3.1. Objectives :

The purpose of the study is to examine impact of Maternal Healthcare Financing Schemes on Maternal Healthcare Utilization. To address this issue, the following objectives have been put forth:

- to evaluate the impact of Maternal Healthcare Financing Schemes on utilization of Antenatal Care;
- to assess the impact of Maternal Healthcare Financing Schemes on utilization of Delivery Care; and
- to examine the impact of Maternal Healthcare Financing Schemes on utilization of Postnatal Care.

3.2. Hypotheses :

To achieve the above-mentioned objectives, following hypotheses have been set:

H1. Maternal Healthcare Financing Schemes have a significant impact on utilization of Antenatal Care.

H2. Maternal Healthcare Financing Schemes significantly influence utilization of Delivery Care.

H3. There is a significant difference between Treatment Group and Comparison Group with regard to utilization of Postnatal Care.

4. Sample Selection and Methodology

4.1. Study Design and Data Collection :

The present study has been conducted in Kashmir Division of Union Territory, Jammu and Kashmir, India. Kashmir valley is the north most region of the Indian subcontinent, characterized by its harsh weather conditions, remains cut-off from the rest of country for a long period during winters which further adds to the sufferings of poor people. For assessing the impact using Non-experimental Design, a problem of selection bias arises which can be mitigated with the help of using Quasi-Experimental Design (Weber and Ahmad, 2014; Tariq and Sangmi, 2020). Therefore, to evaluate the impact of Maternal Healthcare Financing Schemes on Maternal Utilization, the Quasi-Experimental Survey Design has been employed, whereby matching of a Treatment Group with the Comparison Group is made. The Treatment group consists of 50 participants and the Comparison Group comprises 50 respondents. In total, the study has 100 respondents, the selection of the sample is based on the information of beneficiaries enrolled under two schemes (JSY and JSSK) supplied by the Office of the Mission Director, Jammu and Kashmir National Health Mission to the researchers. With the support of ASHAs, each non-participant respondent for comparison is chosen from the same vicinity as a participant respondent, taking due cognizance that the attributes (like place of residence, age, parity, occupation, education, awareness, and income levels) of participant and non-participant are similar. The matching has been done on the two groups of respondents regarding these attributes. Thus, primary data has been collected from women of reproductive age who had a live birth within the previous twelve months before the survey (conducted in 2021-22). As such, the reference period for the study is one year. Using a well-structured and pretested Interview Schedule, a Multistage Stratified Sampling technique has been used for the survey to obtain a sample size of 100 respondents. Among all the 10 districts, two districts have been selected viz., Anantnag and Srinagar in the first stage as these districts had the largest population of beneficiaries enrolled in the schemes under evaluation for the study period. In the second stage of sampling, three blocks from each of the identified districts with higher enrolment were selected. In the third stage,

data has been collected from Treatment and Comparison Group respondents from each block (in proportion to the number of beneficiaries in each block), which represents a district and, eventually, the whole Kashmir valley. The Construct Maternal Healthcare Utilization has been measured on a four-point Likert-type Scale and the main dimensions analyzed relate to Antenatal Care, Delivery Care and Postnatal Care. These dimensions have been fully explained in Appendix-I.

4.2. Data Processing and Analysis :

For analysis, data has been entered into MS-Excel, then exported to Smart PLS-3 for testing reliability and validity of the scale and subsequently to the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 26.0 for final analysis. Since the data from both Treatment and Comparison Group was found to be normally distributed, an Independent Samples Test with Effect Size (r) will suffice for the study's objectives and assist in testing the above formulated hypotheses. The Effect Size values reflect the importance of impact in practical terms with $r = .2$ indicates a small effect, $r = .5$ represents a moderate effect and $r = .8$ or $>$ shows large effect (Tariq and Sangmi, 2020).

5. Results and Discussion

After the data has been collected and analyzed with the help of statistical techniques, the results of the survey have been scientifically validated and interpreted, thus described under the following heads:

5.1. Socio-Demographic Profile of the Sample Respondents :

The socio-demographic characteristics of the sample have been given in Table-1. Out of 100 respondents, fifty percent are from Srinagar and fifty percent from Anantnag district of Kashmir Valley with equal number of respondents taken for Treatment and Comparison Group. 67 percent have been from rural areas, whereas 33 percent from urban areas with a mean difference of 0.34 which is also statistically significant indicating that place of residence has a bearing on utilization of maternal healthcare. Muslim religion was followed by majority of respondents in both the groups (86%) followed by Hindu religion (11%), and Sikh religion (3%). The difference is significant at 5%. The main findings suggest that majority of sample respondents are in the young age group of 25-29 years (43%), with a zero percentage in the adolescent age group of 15-19 years. Around half of the women (55%) have only had one child, while nearly a quarter (11%) have had more than three children. This is again statistically significant

($p = 0.0124$) indicating that this covariate influences the utilization as first babies typically receive more attention from the mothers since they are less accustomed to and are, therefore, more willing to seek out modern healthcare facilities. Moreover, half of the research participants (69%) are home-makers, with only a small percentage (27%) working outside home. However, 21% of fathers and 13% of mothers do not have a formal education. The majority of respondents (26% + 31% = 57%) have less awareness about government programs, though ASHA stands out as the primary source of information (78%). More than half of the participants (62%) were classified as being below the poverty line, and a significant number of households from both the groups (48%) had a monthly income of less than ₹10000 (INR). The mean difference (5.2512) for comparison between the two groups is statistically significant ($p = 0.000$), illustrating that majority of the beneficiaries are poor. This also shows the level of targeting of the schemes to the poor.

5.2. Reliability and Validity of the Scale :

The Maternal Healthcare Utilization Scale has been appropriately developed and validated after taking into consideration prior literature and thorough discussion with the experts of the field. Cronbach's Alpha (α), Composite Reliability (CR), and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) have been used to examine the Reliability and Validity (convergent) of the latent variables.

Cronbach's alpha (α) is a way of assessing reliability by comparing the amount of shared variance, or covariance, among the items making up an instrument to the amount of overall variance. The acceptable value for α is 0.6 to 0.7. However, the value above 0.7 is preferred (Hair et al., 2011).

Composite Reliability (CR) is a measure of internal consistency, which means that each of the measures consistently represents the same latent construct. It is calculated as follows: Sum of Squared Standardized Loadings divided by Sum of Squared Standardized Loadings plus Sum of Error Variance. A CR of 0.7 is considered satisfactory. However, a value of 0.6 to 0.7 is considered acceptable if other indicators of a model's Construct Validity are satisfactory (Hair et al., 2010).

The variance in the observed variables explained by the common latent variable presents the *Average Variance Extracted* (AVE). The formula for calculating AVE is : Sum of Squared Standardized Factor Loadings divided by the number of items. A value of AVE greater than 0.50 for each latent construct is considered acceptable (Hair et al., 2010).

Table-1 : Socio-Demographic Profile of Respondents (N=100).

Indicator	Category		%	Mean Diff. for comparison between the two groups	t-value for comparison between the two groups	p-value				
Place of Residence	Rural	Treatment	41	0.34	-3.7764	0.0003				
		Comparison	26							
	Urban	Treatment	9							
		Comparison	24							
Total			100							
Religion	Muslim	Treatment	46	0.18	2.028	0.0453				
		Comparison	40							
	Hindu	Treatment	4							
		Comparison	7							
	Sikh	Treatment	0	100						
		Comparison	3							
	Total									
	Age	15-19	Treatment				0	0.36	2.263	0.0258
Comparison			0							
20-24		Treatment	14							
		Comparison	4							
25-29		Treatment	21							
		Comparison	22							
30-34		Treatment	12							
		Comparison	22							
Total			100							
Parity	1	Treatment	23	0.34	-2.5481	0.0124				
		Comparison	31							
	2	Treatment	17							
		Comparison	18							
3 or More	Treatment	10								
	Comparison	1								
Total			100							
Occupation of Respondent	Govt. Service	Treatment	0	0.34	-2.5481	0.0124				
		Comparison	0							
	Private Service	Treatment	7							
		Comparison	20							
	Farming	Treatment	0							
		Comparison	0							
	Labour	Treatment	4							
		Comparison	0							
Home Maker	Treatment	39								
	Comparison	30								
Total			100							
Occupation of Spouse	Govt. Service	Treatment	0	1.12	-6.8953	0.000				
		Comparison	0							
	Private Service	Treatment	16							
		Comparison	44							
	Farming	Treatment	0							
		Comparison	0							
Labour	Treatment	34								
	Comparison	6								
Total			100							
Education of Respondent	No Education	Treatment	11	0.48	2.1503	0.034				
		Comparison	2							
	Primary	Treatment	8							
		Comparison	11							
	Secondary	Treatment	15							
		Comparison	8							
	Higher Secondary	Treatment	12							
		Comparison	29							
Higher Education	Treatment	4								
	Comparison	0								
Total			100							

Education of Spouse	No Education	Treatment	21	0.78	3.5159	0.0007	
		Comparison	0				
	Primary	Treatment	10				
		Comparison	16				
	Secondary	Treatment	12				
		Comparison	18				
	Higher Secondary	Treatment	1				
		Comparison	16				
	Higher Education	Treatment	6				
		Comparison	0				
Total		100					
Awareness about JSY	No Awareness	Treatment	11	0.38	2.0131	0.0468	
		Comparison	7				
	Less Awareness	Treatment	17				
		Comparison	9				
	Moderate Awareness	Treatment	16				
		Comparison	25				
	High Awareness	Treatment	6				
		Comparison	9				
	Total		100				
	Awareness about JSSK	No Awareness	Treatment				21
Comparison			10				
Less Awareness		Treatment	23				
		Comparison	20				
Moderate Awareness		Treatment	4				
		Comparison	16				
High Awareness		Treatment	2				
		Comparison	4				
Total			100				
Source of Information about Govt. Scheme/s		ASHA	Treatment	40	0.58	-2.1858	0.0312
	Comparison		38				
	ANM	Treatment	6				
		Comparison	0				
	Doctor	Treatment	0				
		Comparison	2				
	Govt. Publicity/Print/Electronic Media	Treatment	4				
		Comparison	10				
	Total		100				
	Status of Household	BPL	Treatment	36			
Comparison			26				
APL		Treatment	14				
		Comparison	24				
Total			100				
Monthly Income Level of Household		Upto ₹5000	Treatment	12	0.92	5.2512	0.000
	Comparison		0				
	₹5001-₹10000	Treatment	20				
		Comparison	16				
	₹10001-₹15000	Treatment	18				
		Comparison	22				
	₹15001-₹20000	Treatment	0				
		Comparison	6				
	₹20001 or Above	Treatment	0				
		Comparison	6				
Total		100					

*Significant at 5%

Source: Field survey by the researchers

Table-2 shows the results for reliability and validity (convergent), as well as the factor loadings, for the entire sample. All of the alpha values are greater than the recommended value of 0.70. For all variables, the CR and AVE is greater than 0.70 and 0.50 respectively, indicating convergent validity.

Table-2 : Item Loadings, Reliability and Validity (Convergent).

Utilization	Item	λ	α	CR	AVE	VIF
Antenatal Care	Rec_ANC	0.807	0.740	0.825	0.507	4.997
	Rec_IFA	0.601				1.629
	Rec_TTs	0.665				1.923
	Ist_ANC	0.801				3.721
	RecANC_Doctor	0.931				1.896
	RecANC_ANM	0.617				1.510
	RecANC_DH/PHC/CHC/SC	0.537				3.111
	RecANC_PvtHos	0.763				6.529
Delivery Care	TypDel_Normal	0.881	0.748	0.822	0.501	3.716
	TypDel_CSection	0.703				4.764
	PlcDel_GovtInst	0.892				4.682
	PlcDelPvtInst	0.621				3.955
	Del_SBA	0.502				1.714
	Del_TBA	0.769				4.994
	FacPDC_Normal	0.902				1.565
	FacPDC_CSection	0.836				4.084
Postnatal Care	Rec_PNC	0.883	0.744	0.846	0.595	2.919
	RecPNC_42	0.883				4.104
	RecPNC_Doc/ANM	0.843				4.289
	RecPNC_DH/PHC/CHC/SC	0.501				3.518
	RecPNC_PvtHos	0.783				4.107

Source: Field survey by the researchers

Moreover, the Fornell-Larcker criterion and the Heterotrait-Monotrait Method (HTMT) have been used to examine Discriminant Validity, with the results shown in Table-3.

The *Fornell and Larcker (1981)* Criterion states that Discriminant Validity is established when a construct's square root of AVE is greater than its correlation with all other constructs. In the current study, square root of AVE (in bold and italics) for each construct was found to be greater than its correlation with other constructs (Table-3).

Also, the estimation of the correlation between the constructs underpins *HTMT Method*. The HTMT threshold has been debated in the existing literature; Kline (2011) argued a conservative threshold of 0.85 or less, while Teo et al. (2008) proposed a liberal threshold of 0.90 or less. According to Table-3, the HTMT ratio for all constructs is less than the required threshold of 0.90. The establishment of discriminant validity is, thus, strongly supported.

Table-3 : Discriminant Validity using the Fornell & Larcker Criterion and HTMT Method.

	Fornell & Larcker Criterion			HTMT		
	Antenatal Care	Delivery Care	Postnatal Care	Antenatal Care	Delivery Care	Postnatal Care
Antenatal Care	<i>0.712</i>					
Delivery Care	0.533	<i>0.684</i>		0.519		
Postnatal Care	0.526	0.592	<i>0.771</i>	0.515	0.643	

Source: Field survey by the researchers

Note: Bold and Italicized elements are the square root of AVE.

5.3. Impact of Maternal Healthcare Financing Schemes on Utilization of Antenatal Care :

The study attempts to address utilization of Antenatal Care in terms of eight indicators-No. of ANC's received; No. of Iron and Folic Acid Tablets (IFA) received;No. of Tetanus Toxoid Injections (TTs) received; No. of ANC's received in the first trimester of pregnancy; ANC received by Doctor/Auxiliary Nurse Midwife (ANM); ANC received at District Hospital/Primary Health Centre/Community Health Centre/Sub-Centre and ANC received at Private Hospital. Utilization of Antenatal Care for the two independent groups of respondents, Treatment and Comparison Groups, has been compared using an Independent Samples t-Test. The results encapsulated in Table-4 indicate that there have been significant differences in the scores, [$t(92.599) = 6.088, p = 0.000$], with the mean score for Treatment Group ($m = 1.9425, SD = .29147$) being higher than the Comparison Group ($m = 1.5350, SD = .37290$). Equal variances have not been assumed because p value corresponding to F Statistic is less than 0.05. The magnitude of the mean differences (mean difference = .40750, 95% CI: .2745 to .54043) is significant. As a result, the findings suggest that Maternal Healthcare Financing Schemes have a significant positive impact on Antenatal Care Utilization.

However, Effect Size has been used to calculate the magnitude of the impact on each indicator and on the composite Antenatal Care score. The effect size ($r = 1.217, i.e., > 0.8$) on the overall Antenatal Care score is quite high, indicating large impact.

Table-4 : Impact of Maternal Healthcare Financing Schemes on Utilization of ANC: Statistical Analysis

Indicator	Group Statistics		t-test for Equality of Means											
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		Effect Size (r)
			Equal variances assumed	Equal variances not assumed								Lower	Upper	
Rec ANC	Treatment	2.80	0.404	25.877	.000	3.724	98	.000	.340	.091	.159	.521	.7448	
	Comparison	2.46	0.503			3.724	93.614	.000	.340	.091	.159	.521		
Rec IFA	Treatment	1.52	0.580	5.771	.018	2.023	98	.046	.220	.109	.004	.436	.4046	
	Comparison	1.30	0.505			2.023	96.186	.046	.220	.109	.004	.436		
Rec TTs	Treatment	2.44	0.501	15.925	.000	2.763	98	.007	.260	.094	.073	.447	.5526	
	Comparison	2.18	0.438			2.763	96.234	.007	.260	.094	.073	.447		
1 st ANC	Treatment	2.60	0.495	2.699	.104	4.724	98	.000	.520	.110	.302	.738	.9948	
	Comparison	2.08	0.601			4.724	94.538	.000	.520	.110	.301	.739		
RecANC by Doctor/ANM	Treatment	2.58	0.642	5.784	.018	6.352	98	.000	.920	.145	.633	1.207	1.270	
	Comparison	1.66	0.798			6.352	93.678	.000	.920	.145	.632	1.208		
RecANC at DH/PHC/CHC/SC	Treatment	1.72	.757	0.002	.965	.823	98	.412	.120	.146	-.169	.409	.1646	
	Comparison	1.60	0.700			.823	97.402	.412	.120	.146	-.169	.409		
RecANC at Pvt Hos.	Treatment	1.38	0.725	39.367	.000	11.151	98	.000	1.280	.115	1.052	1.508	2.2302	
	Comparison	0.10	0.364			11.151	72.232	.000	1.280	.115	1.052	1.509		
Composite Score	Treatment	1.9425	0.29147	5.305	.023	6.088	98	.000	.40750	.06693	.27467	.54033	1.217	
	Comparison	1.5350	0.37290			6.088	92.599	.000	.40750	.06693	.27467	.54033		

Source: Field survey by the researchers

5.4. Impact of Maternal Healthcare Financing Schemes on Utilization of Delivery Care :

Utilization of Delivery Care has been measured with the help of six indicators – type of delivery used as Normal; type of delivery used as Caesarean Section; delivery assisted by Skilled Birth Attendant (SBA); delivery assisted by Traditional Birth Attendant (TBA); Post-delivery complication faced after normal delivery and Post-delivery complications faced after Caesarean Section. Similarly, an Independent Samples t-Test has been conducted to compare the Utilization of Delivery Care for two independent groups of participants i.e., Treatment and Comparison Groups. Taking the overall composite score for Delivery Care, as summarized in Table-5, equal variances have not been assumed as p value corresponding to F Statistic is less than 0.05, there have been significant differences, [t (57.451) = -10.598, p = 0.000] in the scores with mean score for Treatment Group (m = .8235, SD = .26560) is higher than the Comparison Group (m = .4175, SD = .07829). The magnitude of the differences in the means (mean difference = 0.41500, 95% CI: -.49271 to -.33729) is significant. Hence, the results indicate that Maternal Healthcare Financing Schemes have a significant favourable impact on Utilization of Delivery Care. The effect size indicates quite significant impact (r = 2.12 i.e., > 0.8) on the overall score of Delivery Care.

5.5. Impact of Maternal Healthcare Financing Schemes on Utilization of Postnatal Care :

Furthermore, five indicators have been employed for measuring utilization of Postnatal Care namely No. of PNCs received; No. of PNCs received in less than 42 days after delivery, PNC received by Doctor/ANM; PNC received at District Hospital/Primary Health Centre/Community Health Centre/Sub-Centre and PNC received at Private Hospital. An Independent Samples t-Test is used to compare Postnatal Care Utilization for two independent respondent groups, Treatment and Comparison. As indicated in Table-6, there are significant differences in the scores, [t (83.773) = 6.890, p = 0.000], with the Treatment Group's mean score (m = 1.8200, SD = .41845) being higher than the Comparison Group's (m = 1.0680, SD = .64853). Because p value corresponding to F Static is less than 0.05, equal variances have just not been assumed. The mean differences are significant (mean difference = .75200, 95% CI: .53493 to .96907). Thereby, the analysis reveal that Maternal Healthcare Financing Schemes appear to have a significant beneficial impact on Utilization of Postnatal Care. Besides, the effect size on the overall Postnatal Care score (r = 1.38, i.e., >0.8) is fairly large, implying a significant influence.

Table-5 : Impact of Maternal Healthcare Financing Schemes on Utilization of DC : Statistical Analysis
Independent Samples Test

Indicator	Group Statistics	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances										t-test for Equality of Means			
		Mean	Std. Deviation	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		Effect Size (r)		
											Lower	Upper			
Type of Del as Normal	Treatment Comparison	.78	.418	11.714	.001	-9.307	98	.000	-.680	.073	-.825	-.353	1.86		
	Comparison	.10	.303			-9.307	89.310	.000	-.680	.073	-.825	-.353			
Type of Del as C-Section	Treatment Comparison	.96	.198	5.792	.018	-1.172	98	.244	-.060	.051	-.162	.042	.234		
	Comparison	.90	.303			-1.172	84.374	.244	-.060	.051	-.162	.042			
Del assisted by SBA	Treatment Comparison	1.00	.000	20.444	.000	-2.064	98	.042	-.080	.039	-.157	-.003	.413		
	Comparison	.92	.274			-2.064	49.000	.044	-.080	.039	-.158	-.002			
Del assisted by TBA	Treatment Comparison	.74	.443	.865	.355	-6.033	98	.000	-.520	.068	-.691	-.349	1.21		
	Comparison	.22	.418			-6.033	97.681	.000	-.520	.068	-.691	-.349			
Faced PDC after Normal Delivery	Treatment Comparison	.78	.418	27.254	.000	-	98	.000	-.740	.071	-.882	-.598	2.072		
	Comparison	.04	.283			10.360			-.740	.071	-.882	-.598			
Faced PDC after C-Section	Treatment Comparison	.74	.443	6.192	.015	-7.102	98	.000	-.580	.082	-.742	-.418	1.420		
	Comparison	.16	.370			-7.102	95.007	.000	-.580	.082	-.742	-.418			
Composite Score	Treatment Comparison	.8235	.26560	69.326	.000	-	98	.000	-.41500	.03916	-	-	2.12		
	Comparison	.4175	.07829			10.598			-.41500	.03916	-.49271	.33729			
							57.451	.000	-.41500	.03916	-	-			
							10.598				.49271	.33729			

Source: Field survey by the researchers
 Note: SBA-Skilled Birth Attendant; TBA-Traditional Birth Attendant; PDC-Post Delivery Complications.

Table-6 : Impact of Maternal Healthcare Financing Schemes on Utilization of PNC : Statistical Analysis

Indicator	Group	Independent Samples Test											
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances					t-test for Equality of Means						
		Mean	Std. Deviation	F	Sig.	T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	Effect Size (r)	
Rec PNC	Treatment	2.02	.589	5.296	.024	6.752	98	.000	.920	.136	.650	1.190	1.35
	Comparison	1.10	.763			6.752	92.091	.000	.920	.136	.649	1.191	
Rec PNC in less than 42 days	Treatment	2.08	.601	21.901	.000	5.151	98	.000	.780	.151	.479	1.081	1.03
	Comparison	1.30	.886			5.151	86.166	.000	.780	.151	.479	1.081	
Rec PNC by Doctor/ANM	Treatment	2.16	.510	26.382	.000	4.565	98	.000	.660	.145	.373	.947	.913
	Comparison	1.50	.886			4.565	78.192	.000	.660	.145	.372	.948	
Rec PNC at DH/PHC/CH	Treatment	1.64	.749	3.692	.058	-4.083	98	.000	-6.60	.162	-.981	-.339	.817
	Comparison	1.30	.863			-4.083	96.109	.000	-6.60	.162	-.981	-.339	
Rec PNC at Pvt Hospital	Treatment	2.20	1.010	17.805	.000	12.363	98	.000	2.060	.167	1.729	2.391	2.47
	Comparison	.14	.606			12.363	80.259	.000	2.060	.167	1.728	2.392	
Composite Score	Treatment	1.8200	.41845	13.306	.000	6.890	98	.000	.75200	.10915	.53539	.96861	1.38
	Comparison	1.0680	.64853			6.890	83.773	.000	.75200	.10915	.53493	.96907	

Source: Field survey by the researchers

6. Conclusion

Maternal Healthcare Utilization has been assessed by studying the utilization of antenatal, delivery and postnatal care. The present study indicates that JSY Scheme followed by JSSK has been able to enhance access to and utilization of all the three maternal services, the reason being cash assistance provided by JSY which has further been followed by the cashless entitlements furnished by JSSK. As a result of the intervention, expectant women are significantly more likely to seek care from qualified providers for ANC, DC and PNC. Since it is a well acknowledged fact that maternal mortality can be reduced with increased institutional deliveries, deliveries conducted by skilled birth attendants and when women have access to emergency obstetric care. The present study seems to meet all the pre-conditions, thereby concluding that the schemes have made a positive impact on decreasing maternal mortality in the study area. These results have been corroborated by a number of studies, for instance, using quasi-experimental framework, Lim et al. (2010); Rahman and Pallikadavath (2018) reported significant positive impact on the uptake of maternal healthcare. However, the contribution of JSY can be seen in increased institutionalization of deliveries far greater than ANC and PNC, indicating the limited role of the program in comprehensively addressing the maternal care needs. This is in line with the findings of Gopalan and Durairaj (2012); Ali et al. (2019). Thus, this study aims to contribute significantly to the current literature on the impact of Maternal Healthcare Financing Schemes for increasing Maternal Healthcare Utilization in terms of all the three maternal services and not only delivery care which most researchers have addressed. The study concludes that there are statistically significant differences between the two groups, with the Treatment Group having a significantly higher mean score than the Comparison Group for each of the indicators of ANC, DC and PNC, as indicated by the Independent Samples Test. However, the findings show that there are still gaps among beneficiaries and non-beneficiaries regarding awareness of the availability of cashless services in government institutions. The loopholes are especially noticeable when it comes to the JSSK Scheme's free and cashless benefits. Consequently, awareness generation and service provision are the top priority are as for further strengthening the intervention.

Appendix-I

Operational Definitions :

To evaluate the impact on Maternal Healthcare Utilization, outcome variables have been identified as Maternal Healthcare Utilization (ANC, DC and PNC),

independent variables consisting socio-demographic indicators as place of residence, religion, age, parity, occupation, education, level of awareness, source of information, status of household and household income.

Antenatal Care (ANC) has been defined as a woman having received four or more visits to a health facility, having received at least two Tetanus Toxoid Injections and consuming 100 Iron and Folic Acid tablets. Besides ANC received from Doctor/ANM and at District Hospital/PHC/CHC/SC and Private Hospital have also taken into consideration.

Delivery Care (DC) has been defined as a woman giving birth in a health facility (Public/Private), type of delivery used (Normal/Caesarean Section), assisted by a skilled birth attendant (Doctor/Nurse/ANM). An extension has been made to post-delivery complications.

Postnatal Care (PNC) has been defined as a woman having received three or more PNC visits with a qualified provider (Doctor/Nurse/ANM), received PNC At DH/PHC/CHC/SC and Private Hospital.

Compliance with Ethical Requirement

Informed Consent : Taken

Declaration of Conflicting Interests

The authors declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship and/or publication of this paper.

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